

CRITERIA AND FACTORS OF FORMATION OF VOCAL PERFORMANCE SKILLS IN PRIMARY GRADE STUDENTS

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Annotation: This thesis covers the pedagogical and psychological foundations of the formation of vocal performance skills in primary school students. The criteria for selecting age-appropriate vocal exercises for children, developing musical hearing, breathing techniques, and expressive singing skills are analyzed on a scientific basis. The main factors influencing the formation of vocal performance are also studied - teacher skills, musical environment, methodological approaches in the lesson process, and the role of individual approaches. According to the results of the study, a systematic, step-by-step approach is important for the development of vocal abilities in primary school students.

Keywords: vocal performance, musical education, singing ability, methodological approach, vocal exercises, children's voice, expressive performance, breathing techniques.

Introduction.

One of the powerful tools that moves the human soul, awakens feelings and educates the psyche is music. Music, especially in childhood, plays an important role in the formation of a person's aesthetic worldview, taste and speech culture. In particular, a child who is familiar with the art of vocal performance from a young age achieves significant achievements not only in terms of musical, but also in terms of general development. Therefore, the formation of vocal performance skills in primary school students is recognized as one of the urgent tasks of today's educational process.

In modern music education, the need to open up vocal possibilities, teach singing techniques and direct them to expressive performance on the basis of an individual approach to each child is increasingly increasing. Because in today's globalization environment, the development of aesthetic education, musical culture and creative thinking of children serves their socialization, self-confidence and the formation of communicative competencies. Especially at the stage of primary education, the gradual and scientifically based development of vocal performance skills creates a solid foundation for their subsequent musical activity. This thesis is aimed at highlighting the theoretical and practical aspects of this issue, namely, identifying the criteria and factors that serve to form vocal

performance skills in primary school students. This is intended to introduce modern approaches to the educational process and increase the effectiveness of the pedagogical process. The relevance of the thesis is that it enriches the content of the musical education process and allows children to discover their inner world through musical expression. Primary school is an important stage not only in acquiring knowledge, but also in the comprehensive formation of a person. It is during this period that the child's musical worldview, listening culture and vocal abilities are rapidly and actively formed. Vocal performance serves as the heart, the central element of this process. Because through singing, the child expresses his feelings, boldly steps into the world of sounds, learns to hear and make himself heard. Vocal performance is not just singing, but the art of expressing thoughts in harmony with deep inner feelings, technical skills and music. These aspects are especially important when working with primary school students. This is because they are still at the initial stage of developing their vocal cords and are very fragile physically and emotionally. In such conditions, the right approach, careful methodology and the personality of a teacher who is kind to musical education are decisive factors in developing their vocal abilities. In the formation of vocal performance, it is necessary to pay attention to several criteria. First of all, this is to determine the natural vocal capabilities of the child, that is, his vocal range, intonation accuracy, and breath control skills. Secondly, the ability to hear and repeat music, develop a sense of rhythm, and play the melody correctly. Thirdly, expressive singing, that is, the ability to create an image through a musical text and convey it through feeling. Each of these criteria requires its own approach and training. For example, special breathing exercises should be used to develop the child's ability to breathe correctly and use it in the voice. To work on intonation, it is advisable to conduct training through games and songs on hearing and distinguishing musical intervals. The most important thing is to arouse interest in these processes in the child and to instill a love of music.

At the same time, there are also key factors that influence the development of vocal performance. These are the professional level and taste of the teacher, the methodological organization of music lessons, the family and social environment, as well as the school's attitude to cultural life. If a child is brought up in an environment where he feels free, supported and oriented towards creativity, then vocal performance skills will naturally form. So, the formation of vocal abilities in primary school students is not a simple process - it is a complex, but extremely enjoyable path consisting of a combination of musical,

pedagogical and psychological approaches. Each child has his own inner musical world, and opening this world is in the hands of us teachers. And vocal classes are one of the most elegant doors that open to this world.

Discussion:

Today, the importance of music, and in particular vocal performance, in the educational process is increasing. Because musical education, especially vocal classes, directly affect the child's spiritual world, forming his aesthetic taste, speech culture, ability to hear and feel. From this perspective, the effective implementation of vocal performance activities in primary school requires not only professional skills from each teacher, but also love for children, deep devotion to music.

The study confirmed the need for a systematic approach to developing vocal performance skills in students. At the initial stages, the most important thing for a child is to be able to freely express himself through music. After all, vocal performance is not only the art of singing correctly, but also the art of expressing the inner world through melody. It is in primary school that children learn to play with their voice, breathe in tune, and create an image. In this process, the teacher's guidance, motivating approach, and correct methodological applications play a decisive role.

Discussions show that the main factors that positively affect the development of vocal abilities are the individual approach of the teacher, the suitability of the exercises used for the age of the children, the emotional richness of the lessons, and the presence of a creative environment. On the contrary, working in the wrong style, not taking into account the child's vocal capabilities, a harsh approach, or criticism of mistakes can extinguish their interest in vocals. Therefore, not only technical skills, but also pedagogical sensitivity are very important when working with children. Another important aspect is that children's success in vocal performance does not depend only on the knowledge gained at school. This process is also strongly influenced by the family, environment, and cultural activities of children. In particular, factors such as the parents' attitude to music, listening to music at home, and involving the child in cultural activities have a positive effect on his or her vocal activity. Thus, the formation of vocal performance is not just teaching singing, but also educating the child's soul, giving it the opportunity to feel, express and create. This requires a new approach from modern educators, along with musical knowledge, love from the heart. Vocal performance is a form of childhood

dreams transformed into melody, and its preservation and development is in our hands.

Conclusion.

Music is the language of the soul, and vocals are one of the most expressive means of this language. It is in the primary school years that a child learns to hear music with his heart, to express words in melody. He begins to express his feelings, joy, surprise and even sadness through singing. This is a true miracle of musical education - the gradual formation of vocal performance skills. The above observations and analyses show that the development of vocal performance skills is a complex, but extremely enjoyable and creative process. The success of this process depends on many factors: the characteristics of the child's voice, the level of musical hearing, the ability to breathe correctly, the quality of methodological training, the teacher's approach, and most importantly - the child's interest and enthusiasm. Not every child may be born with a unique vocal talent, but every child has an inner need to sing, a desire to express it. The task of the teacher is to be able to see this need, to guide it with love and develop it through modern methodological approaches.

Vocal training not only increases musical potential, but also forms confidence, stage culture, teamwork, emotional thinking and creative thinking in the child. All this creates the basis for the child's development as a person. Therefore, the formation of vocal performance skills in the process of primary education is extremely important, as it serves not only musical goals, but also general educational and developmental goals. In short, every child has a world hidden in a musical melody. It is up to us, the teachers, to listen to it, hear it and help it open. Through vocal performance, the child finds himself, and his voice expresses the life in his soul.

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